

A Study of the Complexes Formed from the So-called Ethereal Blue Peroxychromic Acid with Quinoline, 8-Hydroxyquinoline, and Strychnine

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Different samples of quinoline, 8-hydroxyquinoline, and strychnine complexes with ethereal blue peroxychromic acid have been prepared and analysed. Empirical and molecular formulas of the complexes suggest that the ethereal blue compound is chromium peroxychromate.

From the study of the so-called blue peroxychromic acid with various nitrogenous organic bases or other basic substances, Riesenfeld and co-workers¹ and Wiede² concluded the blue peroxychromic acid to have a formula HCrO_5 . Schwarz and Gieso³ also prepared the pyridine complex of the acid (by Wiede's method) and from the study of this complex they assigned to it the formula PyCrO_5 , showing thereby that the blue peroxychromic acid was CrO_5 .

Rai⁴ also prepared the pyridine and piperidine complexes of ethereal blue peroxychromic acid, following Wiede's method. The formulas assigned to pyridine and piperidine complexes were $\text{R}_2\text{Cr}(\text{CrO}_5)$ and $\text{R}_3\text{Cr}(\text{CrO}_5)$ respectively, where R represented one molecule of pyridine or piperidine.

From the above it is clear that different investigators have different opinion regarding the constitution of the so-called blue peroxychromic acid, arrived at by studying its various complexes. Thus, the behaviour of the blue compound towards complex formation with different organic nitrogenous bases calls for further investigations. The work embodied in the present communication is the continuation of Rai's work⁴.

EXPERIMENTAL

The ethereal blue peroxychromic acid was prepared as described earlier by Rai⁴. The chemicals used were H_2O_2 (20 vol., 25 ml), chromic acid solution (5%, w/v, 50 ml), and ether (100 ml).

Quinoline Complex.—To the ethereal blue compound excess of quinoline (double distilled, 25 ml) was added. After keeping this overnight, a dark brown complex was found

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1. Riesenfeld *et al.*, 1905, **38**, 1885, 3380, 4068; 1908, **41**, 3586, 3941.

2. *Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 2178; 1898, **31**, 516, 3139.

3. *Ber.*, 1932, **75B**, 871.

4. *This Journal*, 1957, **34**, 69.

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to be precipitated from the ethereal solution. It was filtered and washed with ether till the filtrate was colorless. It was then dried in a desiccator.

8-Hydroxyquinoline Complex.—This complex was prepared in the same way as the quinoline complex. A green precipitate was obtained immediately after addition of ethereal solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline (10%, 25ml). It was filtered and dried as in the case of the quinoline complex.

Strychnine Complex.—Strychnine was dissolved in rectified spirit and its saturated solution was added to the ethereal blue compound when a canary-yellow complex was immediately precipitated. It was filtered, washed, and dried as usual.

Estimation of Total Chromium.—Definite masses of the three complexes were taken separately in weighed silica crucibles and heated at first slowly and then strongly. The complexes on heating decomposed to Cr_2O_3 . These were weighed and from this, the weight of Cr_2O_3 was found.

Oxidising Powers of the Three Complexes in NaOH Solution (Iodometric Titrations).—Definite masses of the above three complexes were dissolved separately in 2N-NaOH solution (250 ml) and each was made to 500 ml (this may be termed as solution x). Oxidising powers of these solutions were determined as described by Rai⁴.

TABLE I

Sample No.	% Total Cr.	% Cr in basic part. (Method i)	Vol. (ml) of $Na_2S_2O_3$ used (method ii) in titrating			% N.	% Organic base used.
a	b	c	Soln. x.	Product obtained after oxidising soln. x.	Filtrate of $Cr(OH)_3$ pptn.	g	h
A. Quinoline complex.							
1	19.90	9.96	7.55	15.05	7.50	5.37	49.49
2	19.81	10.00	7.40	15.50	7.70	5.40	49.76
3	19.94	9.90	7.80	15.70	7.80	5.31	48.94
B. 8-Hydroxyquinoline complex.							
1	18.77	9.89	5.50	11.40	5.40	5.05	52.35
2	19.11	9.86	5.35	11.00	5.45	5.04	52.20
3	18.77	9.92	5.45	10.80	5.55	5.06	52.50
C. Strychnine complex.							
1	11.52	5.77	10.30	20.50	10.15	6.22	74.22
2	11.58	5.77	10.50	20.80	10.20	6.25	74.57
3	11.52	5.78	10.05	20.35	10.00	6.19	73.86

Note.—Molecular weight determinations of these complexes could not be carried out due to their insolubility in almost all organic solvents. Even if these were dissolved to some extent in one of them, these started decomposing soon after dissolution. Although these all dissolved in alkali, these were converted into chromates.

Estimation of Chromium in the Basic Part and Oxidising Power of the Filtrate.—Estimation of chromium in basic parts of the complexes was carried out in two ways: (i) The first method was the same as that followed by Rai⁴. (ii) In the second method, from the above 500 ml solutions of the three complexes in NaOH solution, 25-ml aliquots were separately taken in conical flasks and were carefully oxidised by boiling with 100 volumes

H_2O_2 . When the oxidation was complete and the frothing had ceased, the flasks were cooled to the room temperature. These solutions were then acidified and KI was added to them. Liberated iodine was titrated as usual with an $N/20$ thiosulphate solution. The ratio of the oxidising powers before and after the oxidation provided the proportion of chromium present in the acidic and basic parts of the complexes.

Estimation of Nitrogen.—Nitrogen of the complexes of the bases was estimated by Dumas' method. The percentages of nitrogen and that of the bases are presented in Table I.

DISCUSSION

It appears from Table I that the empirical formula for the complexes of quinoline and 8-hydroxyquinoline corresponds to $RCrO_3$ and that for the strychnine complex, $RCrO_4$ (where R stands for one molecule of organic bases).

The titre values shown in columns c and e of the table are all same. Similarly the titre values in column d are double the values shown in column c or e. This clearly shows that chromium is present in acidic as well as in basic parts of the complexes in equal proportions. This is further confirmed from the fact that when the complex as such is ignited, the percentage of total chromium thus obtained is double that of chromium obtained in the basic part of the complex (vide columns a and b). Therefore, considering the above data and the chemical properties of the complexes, the molecular formula for the quinoline and 8-hydroxyquinoline complexes may be written as $R_2Cr(CrO_{10})$, $R_4Cr_2(Cr_2O_{20})$ or $R_4Cr_2(CrO_{10})_2$ and for the strychnine complex, as $R_2Cr(CrO_8)$.

The formula of these and specially that of strychnine are similar to that of the formula R_3CrO_8 , suggested for red peroxychromates by Riesenfeld *et al.*¹ Qualitative observation of the behaviour of these complexes with neutral aqueous solution of KI has shown that though these complexes are slightly soluble in aqueous medium, the strychnine complex liberates iodine from KI, whereas the other two do not. These liberate iodine only in acidic medium. Evidently, the complex of the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid with strychnine, rather than those of the other two bases, resembles the red peroxychromate to a greater extent.

Incidentally, though the three complexes have been prepared in a similar way, their physical and chemical properties vary according to the nature of the base employed.

All the above complexes, when experimentally analysed, show the same amount of chromium in the acidic as well as in the basic parts. Thus, from the suggested molecular formulas for the three complexes, it can be concluded that the so-called blue peroxychromic acid is really a chromium peroxychromate.

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